

Effects of the N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor antagonist, MK-801, on spatial memory and influence of the route of administration

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Running title: Impact of MK-801 administration route on cognition

Abstract

The N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor antagonist, MK-801, is widely used to induce memory and learning impairments in preclinical studies. MK-801 is mainly injected intraperitoneally (i.p.) at doses that result in cognitive impairment and induction of motor or sensory disturbances. The aim of this study was to compare the behavioral outcomes when different administration routes (subcutaneous (s.c.) and i.p.) and MK-801 doses (0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 mg/kg) are employed in the Morris water maze (MWM) task. We also assessed the pharmacokinetics of MK-801 in rat blood plasma and its bioavailability in brain tissue.

The concentrations of MK-801 in brain tissue and blood plasma were significantly higher after s.c. than i.p. administration. MK-801 administered via the s.c. route at doses of 0.1 and 0.05 mg/kg significantly impaired learning on all training days in the MWM task compared to i.p. administration at the same doses. Memory in the probe trial was significantly impaired after MK-801 administration via both routes at all doses. MK-801 also induced locomotor disturbances after i.p. and s.c. administration at the highest dose (0.1 mg/kg).

Our data suggest that s.c. administration leads to higher MK-801 concentrations in brain tissue and blood plasma and evidently impairs spatial learning and memory compared to i.p. administration at the same dose. Knowledge of MK-801 concentrations in the brain and blood and the effects of the compound on memory processes and locomotor activity enable the choice of more targeted routes and doses of administration in preclinical studies.

Keywords i.p. and s.c. administration route, MK-801, Morris water maze, pharmacokinetics, spatial learning, memory

1. Introduction

Currently, approximately 47.5 million people worldwide are diagnosed with dementia. The number of patients with dementia is increasing every year and the World Health Organization expects this number to double by 2030. Validating and improving animal models for cognitive-function studies are therefore crucial. Different animal models are used to investigate the cognitive-enhancing effects of novel drugs [1], and the widely used preclinical behavioral tests to evaluate cognitive function include the passive avoidance test [2], object recognition task for recognition memory [3], the y-maze test and the radial-arm maze test for working and spatial memory assessment [4-6]. The Morris water maze (MWM) task is one of the most commonly used tests in preclinical studies to discover new drugs with spatial memory-enhancing activity [1].

Administration of MK-801 causes cognitive deficits and dementia in rodents when the above-mentioned tests are employed; hence, this form of induction has been widely used in preclinical studies [7,8]. MK-801 (also known as dizocilpine) is a non-competitive antagonist of the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor [8]. NMDA receptors belong to the ionotropic glutamate class of receptors [9] located throughout the brain, and are highly expressed in the hippocampus and the cerebral cortex [10,11]. NMDA receptors are known to mediate synaptic plasticity [12,13], play a major role in memory and learning, and are involved in spatial learning [14,15]. Although MK-801 is a lipophilic compound, it is more often administered via the intraperitoneal (i.p.) than the subcutaneous (s.c.) route (3:1, based on a PubMed literature search, Table 1) in animal studies [16-18]. An overview of studies assessing the effects of MK-801 on spatial learning, memory, and locomotor activity in the MWM task in male rats after s.c. or i.p. administration is shown in Table 1, which only contains publications with the main objective to evaluate the effects of MK-801 using a few drug combinations (i.e., the effect of test substances on MK-801-induced impairment).

In preclinical studies, the most commonly used dose of MK-801 is 0.1 mg/kg i.p.; this not only impairs learning and memory, but also disturbs locomotor activity.

More than 25% of previously published studies have reported a decrease in the swimming speed of animals when MK-801 was used to induce cognitive impairment (Table 1). Concurrently, several studies have reported hyperlocomotion in rats 30 min after an i.p. administration of MK-801 at doses of 0.1 and 0.2 mg/kg. In addition, this has been revealed to persist for up to 70 min in the open-field test [18,19]. Therefore, performing a separate analysis of cognitive impairment and motor or sensory disturbances following MK-801 administration has proven difficult, and serves as a crucial additional setback when a pharmacological model is used to evaluate the activity of novel memory-improving drugs.

The pharmacokinetic profile of MK-801 after i.p. administration has been established in several preclinical studies [17,20,21]; however, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies on its pharmacokinetics when administered via the s.c. route. Therefore, we investigated for the first time the concentration of MK-801 in brain tissue and blood plasma when administered via the s.c. and i.p. routes. The present study was designed to compare behavior outcomes in the MWM task when MK-801 is administered as a cognition-impairing drug via the two most commonly used administration routes, i.p. and s.c, under the same experimental setting.

Table 1. Overview of the effects of MK-801 on spatial learning, memory, and locomotor activity in the MWM task in male rats.

Route of Administration	Dose (mg/kg)	Strain	Impaired spatial learning	Impaired spatial memory	Locomotor activity/swimming speed	Reference
i.p.	0.20	Wistar rats	No	---	---	[22]
		Wistar rats	Yes	No	Hyperlocomotion	[5]
		Long-Evans rats	Yes	Yes	---	[23]
		Wistar rats	Yes	Yes	No	[24]
i.p.	0.15	Wistar rats	Yes	---	No	[25]
		Lewis rats	Yes	---	No	[26]
		Long-Evans rats	Yes	Yes	Hyperlocomotion - increased swimming speed	[27]
i.p.	0.12	Long-Evans rats	Yes	Yes	No	[27]
i.p.	0.10	Wistar	Yes	---	No	[28]

		rats	Yes	Yes	Decreased swimming speed	[6]
			No	---	---	[29]
		Sprague–Dawley rats	Yes	Yes	---	[30]
			Yes	---	No	[18]
		rats	Yes	---	---	[31]
		Long–Evans rats	Yes	Yes	No	[27]
			Yes	---	---	[29]
		Lister rats	Yes	Yes	---	[29]
		Wistar rats	Yes	Yes	No	[7]
s.c.	0.10	Sprague–Dawley rats	Yes	Yes	Decreased swimming speed	[32]
i.p.	0.08	Long–Evans rats	Yes	Yes	No	[27]
s.c.	0.08	Long–Evans rats	Yes	---	---	[27]
s.c.	0.07	Wistar rats	Yes	Yes	No	[7]
		Fisher rats	Yes	No	---	[14]
i.p.	0.05	Long–Evans rats	No	No	No	[27]
		Sprague–Dawley rats	No	---	No	[18]
		Wistar rats	No	No	No	[7]
s.c.	0.05	Sprague–Dawley rats	Yes	Yes	Decreased swimming speed	[32]
		Fischer-344 rats	Yes	---	No	[33]
		Long–Evans rats	Yes	---	---	[34]
s.c.	0.03; 0.01	Sprague–Dawley rats	No	No	No	[32]
	0.01	Long–Evans rats	No	---	---	[34]

The route of administration, dose administered, strain of the experimental rats, effects of the treatment, and references are listed.

Yes –impaired learning and memory observed

No – no impaired behavior observed

"---" – not described/not performed

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals

All studies involving animals were conducted in accordance with ARRIVE guidelines [35,36]. Experimental procedures were performed in accordance with the guidelines reported in the EU Directive 2010/63/EU and local laws and policies. All procedures were approved by the Latvian Animal Protection Ethical Committee of Food and Veterinary Service in Riga, Latvia. Fifty-five naive male Wistar rats weighing 370–420 g at the time of behavioral experiments (Harlan Laboratories BV, Venray, Netherlands and Laboratory Animal Centre), 42 naive male Wistar rats weighing 340–410 g (University of Tartu, Tartu, Estonia) and 30 naive male ICR mice weighing 25–30 g (Harlan Laboratories BV, Venray, Netherlands) at the time of the pharmacokinetics experiments were housed under standard conditions (temperature, 21–23°C; relative humidity, 65% ± 10%; and 12-hour light-dark cycle) with unlimited access to standard food (R70 diet, Lactamin AB, Sweden) and water. Behavioral experiments were conducted during the light period.

2.2. MK-801 administration

MK-801 ([+]-MK-801 hydrogen maleate, Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) was dissolved in sterile saline (0.9% NaCl). For pharmacokinetics evaluation, rats and mice received either a single dose of 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. or s.c. route 15, 30, 60, and 120 min prior to decapitation. Each group consisted of 5 animals for the retrieval of blood and brain samples.

Each day, the MK-801 solutions were prepared fresh before the behavior experiment was conducted and were protected from light between administrations. Animals were divided into three groups with 7 per group receiving a different s.c. dose of MK-801 (0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 mg/kg), three groups with 7 rodents in each receiving a different i.p. dose of MK-801 (0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 mg/kg) and 13 rodents in a control (saline) group. MK-801 or saline was administered i.p. or s.c. 30 min prior to the first MWM swimming task (training trial), for five consecutive days. During the period of drug administration, body weights of the animals were recorded every day.

2.3. Determining the levels of MK-801 in blood plasma and brain tissue using ultra-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry

The concentration of MK-801 in brain tissue and plasma was measured using ultra-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC/MS/MS). After rats were decapitated, blood was collected in heparin-coated tubes and centrifuged at 3000 rpm and 4°C for 10 min to obtain plasma. **Five brains were divided into two hemispheres, and 10 measurements were obtained per result point.** The brain was gently removed and homogenized in ice-cold Milli-Q water at a w/v ratio of 1:5 in 20-s bursts using a Cole Parmer 130-Watt ultrasonic processor set to 40 kHz. The obtained homogenate was centrifuged at 16500 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatant was then decanted, and the pellet was homogenized in the same volume of Milli-Q water as previously used. The obtained homogenate was centrifuged at 16500 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatants were combined and stored at -80°C until use.

Brain tissue extract (300 µL) was mixed with 700 µL of an aqueous solution (v/v) of 2% formic acid, followed by vortex and centrifugation at 13000 rpm for 10 min. A 100-µL volume of rat plasma was then mixed with 900 µL of an aqueous solution (v/v) of 2% formic acid, which was vortexed and centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 10 min. A volume of 950 µL of the supernatant was then loaded onto a conditioned Strata X (33 µm, 30 mg, 1 mL) SPE cartridge (Phenomenex), washed twice with 1 mL of 5% methanol aqueous solution and eluted with 900 µL of 1% formic acid solution in acetonitrile (v/v). The eluent was evaporated using a Genevac EZ-2 at 40°C, reconstituted in 200 µL of mobile phase solution (acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid, 1:1, v/v), and subjected to UPLC/MS/MS analysis. Calibration was performed against external calibration standard solutions.

UPLC was carried out using the Waters Acquity UPLC system equipped with the Acquity BEH C8 column (2.1 × 75 mm, 1.7 µm). The mobile phase consisted of A (aqueous 0.1% formic acid) and B (acetonitrile) at a flow rate of 0.25 mL/min. The following gradient elution was also used: Initial – 50% B, 2.5 min – 98% B, 4.5 min – 98% B, 4.7 min – 50% B, 6 min – 50% B. Injection volume was 5 µL.

MS/MS analysis was performed on a Micromass Quattro Micro™ tandem mass spectrometer in positive ion mode using multiple reaction monitoring of the

transition from m/z 222.2 to 205.2 (cone voltage, 25V; collision energy, 20eV). Quantitative analysis was performed using QuanLynx4.1 software (Waters).

2.4. Morris water maze task

The MWM apparatus was a blue-painted circular fiberglass pool (height: 60 cm, diameter: 150 cm) located in a test room surrounded by several cues, such as cupboards, the experimenter, lamps placed asymmetrically, and posters. These cues were kept constant throughout the test period. The pool was filled to a depth of 35 cm with tap water ($22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$), and virtually divided into four equal imaginary quadrants identified as northeast, northwest, southeast, and southwest. The top surface of the plexiglass platform, which was 10 cm in diameter, was placed 2 cm below the water line at the center of the target (southwest) quadrant throughout the training sessions.

One week before the beginning of the experiment, rats underwent a handling procedure (3 min/day/rat). The animals were trained to swim in the pool for five consecutive days (four trials per day). First, they were gently placed into the water facing the wall of the pool at one of four imaginary starting positions (north, southeast, northwest, and east) around the perimeter of the pool [32,37]. The trials were performed for up to a maximum of 90 s. If the rat could reach the platform, it was allowed to remain there for 15 s, but if it failed to reach the platform within 90 s, it was guided to the platform and allowed to rest on the platform for 15 s. The inter-trial interval was approximately 10-15 min. After the last trial, rats were placed in a drying cage and allowed to dry before they were returned to their home cages. The same procedure was repeated for 4 days. The results are expressed as latency to find the hidden platform.

The retention test (probe trial) was performed 24 h after the last training session with removal of the platform from the pool. The animals were not given post-training treatment or any treatment before the probe trial. All animals could spend 60 s in the pool. All rats began swimming from a position opposite to the quadrant (target quadrant) which contained the platform during their training sessions. In the probe trial, time in the target quadrant, distance until the first crossing of the target quadrant, swimming speed, and number of crossings of the target quadrant were analyzed using a video tracking system (EthoVision[®]; Noldus Information Technology, Wageningen, Netherlands).

2.5. Statistical analysis

All results are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The data of the MWM task was evaluated using two-way or one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Newman-Keuls post-hoc test. MK-801 concentrations in brain tissue and blood plasma were analyzed using unpaired Student's *t*-test. P values less than 0.05 were considered significant. The statistical calculations were performed using GraphPad Prism 3.0 software package (GraphPad Software, Inc., La Jolla, California, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Concentrations of MK-801 in brain tissue and blood plasma

The concentration of MK-801 was measured in blood plasma and brain tissue 15, 30, 60, and 120 min after a single i.p. or s.c. administration of MK-801 at a dose of 0.1 mg/kg. The concentration of MK-801 in the brain was significantly higher after s.c. administration than after i.p. administration at the 15-min ($t_{(18)} = 6.115, p = 0.0001$), 30-min ($t_{(18)} = 3.917, p = 0.001$), and 120-min ($t_{(18)} = 2.797, p = 0.01$) time points (Figure 1A). Fifteen minutes after MK-801 administration, the concentration of the compound in brain tissue was almost 4-fold higher in rats injected via the s.c. route than those injected via the i.p. route ($p = 0.0001$) (Figure 1A).

Figure 1. Concentration of MK-801 in brain tissue and blood plasma. Rats received a s.c. or i.p. injection of MK-801 at a dose of 0.1 mg/kg. Brain tissue (A) and blood plasma (B) samples were collected 15, 30, 60 and 120 min after MK-801 administration. Each point represents the mean (\pm SEM) of five rats per group. The data were analyzed for significant differences using unpaired Student's *t*-test. * $p < 0.05$ vs. the corresponding i.p. group.

Similar effects were observed in blood plasma after MK-801 administration (Figure 1B) at 15 min ($t_{(7)} = 2.914, p = 0.05$) and 30 min ($t_{(7)} = 2.629, p = 0.05$), and the concentration of MK-801 was significantly higher when administered via the s.c. route than via the i.p. route (Figure 1B). MK-801 (dose, 0.1 mg/kg) reached its maximum concentration in brain tissue and blood plasma 15 min after being injected via the s.c. route and 60 min after the i.p. route.

Table 2. Pharmacokinetic parameters of MK-801 after s.c. or i.p. administration in brain tissue and blood plasma.

Administration route	Brain tissue		Blood plasma	
	C_{max} (ng/g)	AUC (ng min/g)	C_{max} (ng/ml)	AUC (ng min/ml)
s.c., 0.1 mg/kg	57.6 ± 7.6	3202 ± 187	7.4 ± 1.6	449 ± 18

i.p., 0.1 mg/kg	37.9 ± 8.9	2640 ± 520	6.8 ± 1.9	405 ± 12
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C_{\max} — maximal concentration; s.c. — subcutaneous; i.p. — intraperitoneal; AUC — area under the curve was calculated from 15 min to 120 min after drug administration. Each point represents the mean (\pm SEM) of five rats per group.

The maximal concentration (C_{\max}) of MK-801 in brain tissue was almost 1.5-fold higher when administered via the s.c. route than the i.p. route (Table 2). In addition, its concentration in brain tissue was 21% higher after s.c. injection than after i.p. injection, as shown by the area under the curve (AUC, Table 2). The MK-801 AUC value for blood was 11% higher when administered via the s.c. route than the i.p. route (Table 2). These results indicate that MK-801 displays better pharmacokinetics in brain tissue and blood plasma when administered via the s.c. than the i.p. route. We observed similar effects of MK-801 administration in mouse blood plasma and brain tissue (Figure S1AB, [38]). C_{\max} of MK-801 in brain tissue was 1.6-fold higher in mice injected via the s.c. route than in rats injected via the s.c. route.

3.2. Effects of MK-801 on spatial learning and memory in the MWM task

The administration route- and dose-related effects of MK-801 on spatial learning and memory were evaluated using the MWM task (Figure 2A, B and C, **main effects of time** ($F_{(4,196)} = 162.2, p < 0.0001$) and **dose** ($F_{(6,49)} = 61.24, p < 0.0001$), and **interaction between time and dose** ($F_{(24,196)} = 5.459, p < 0.0001$)). By s.c.-administering 0.05 and 0.1 mg/kg MK-801, we observed a significant increase in escape latency in rats on all training days when compared to the control group; this indicated impaired learning (Figure 2B and C). In contrast, administering 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. route significantly prolonged escape latency, but only on the first ($p = 0.001$) and second ($p = 0.01$) days of training when compared to the control group (Figure 2C). At a dose of 0.05 mg/kg, the MK-801 administration via the i.p. route had no effect on escape latency. Subcutaneous administration of 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 yielded escape latencies that were almost 3-fold longer than those associated with administration via the i.p. route (Figure 2B). In addition, on all learning days, rats treated with 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the s.c. route had significantly longer escape latencies than the corresponding i.p.-treated animals. The lowest dose, 0.01 mg/kg,

did not affect escape latency despite the route of administration employed (Figure 2A).

Figure 2. Effects of MK-801 on escape latency in the MWM task. Escape latency was measured after s.c. and i.p. administration. MK-801 at doses 0.01 mg/kg (A), 0.05 mg/kg (B) and 0.1 mg/kg (C) was injected 30 min before training (days 1-5). Each value represents mean (\pm SEM) in the MK-801 group ($n=7$) and the saline group ($n=13$). Significant differences were revealed using two-way repeated measures of ANOVA followed by a Newman-Keuls post-hoc test. * $p < 0.05$ vs. saline control group. # $p < 0.05$ vs. the corresponding i.p. group.

The effects of MK-801 on swimming speed were evaluated in the MWM task on all training days (Figure 3A, B, and C) (a significant main effect of dose ($F_{(6,49)} = 7.048$, $p < 0.0001$), but not of time ($F_{(4,192)} = 1.286$, $p > 0.23$) or of the interaction between time and dose ($F_{(24,192)} = 1.204$, $p > 0.24$)). During the training period, the administration of 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the s.c. route significantly reduced swimming speed on all training days when compared to the control group (Figure 3C). In contrast, swimming speed was significantly decreased only on the first training day after this dose was administered via the i.p. route ($p < 0.01$) (Figure 3C). When 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 was administered via the s.c. route, rats showed several motor responses, such as wet-dog shakes and body rolling. The animals could not find the platform or remain on the platform, and thus, had to be guided onto the platform by an experimenter at all times.

Figure 3. The effects of MK-801 on swimming speed in the MWM task. Swimming speed was measured after s.c. and i.p. administration. MK-801 at doses 0.01 mg/kg (A), 0.05 mg/kg (B) and 0.1 mg/kg (C) was injected 30 min before training (days 1–5). Each value represents mean (\pm SEM) in the MK-801 group ($n=7$) and the saline group ($n=13$). Significant differences were found using two-way repeated measures ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls post-hoc test. * $p < 0.05$ vs saline control group.

During the probe trials carried out 24 h following the last day of training, all MK-801-treated rats spent significantly less time in the target quadrant than rats in the control group ($F_{(6,48)} = 19.51, p < 0.0001$) (Figure 4A). Rats injected with MK-801 via the s.c. route spent significantly less time in the target quadrant in a dose-dependent manner compared to rats in the control group. In addition, rats treated with a 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 dose via the s.c. route spent almost 30% less time in the target quadrant than the corresponding i.p.-treated animals (Figure 4A); rats in the 0.1 mg/kg s.c. group spent almost three-fold less time in the target quadrant than their corresponding i.p.-treated animals 24 h after the last day of training.

Figure 4. Spatial memory of MK-801-treated rats in the MWM task on the probe day. Percentage of time spent in the target quadrant 24 h after the last training session (A). Percentage of time spent in each quadrant 24 h after the last training session (B). Animals

were not administered MK-801 before the probe trial. Each value represents mean (\pm SEM) in the MK-801 group ($n = 7$) and saline group ($n = 13$). Data analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls post-hoc test. * $p < 0.05$ vs. saline control group. # $p < 0.05$ vs. the corresponding i.p. group. \$ $p < 0.05$ vs. the corresponding i.p. group.

Rats in the control group spent almost 3.5-fold more time in the target quadrant than the other three quadrants ($F_{(3,48)} = 69.83, p < 0.0001$) (Figure 4B). Rats treated with 0.01 mg/kg MK-801 via the s.c. ($F_{(3,24)} = 13.39, p < 0.0001$) and i.p. ($F_{(3,24)} = 19.83, p < 0.0001$) routes spent almost 2-fold more time in the target quadrant than in the other three quadrants (Figure 4B). However, rats treated with 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 via the s.c. route spent a similar amount of time in all four quadrants ($F_{(3,24)} = 1.148, p > 0.35$), whereas rats treated with 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. route spent almost 35% more time in the target quadrant than in the right and left quadrants ($F_{(3,24)} = 6.956, p < 0.002$). Interestingly, rats treated with 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the s.c. route spent 3.7-fold more time in the opposite quadrant than in the target quadrant ($F_{(3,24)} = 15.21, p < 0.0001$; Figure 4B), whereas rats treated with 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. route spent a similar amount of time in the target and opposite quadrants ($F_{(3,24)} = 5.547, p < 0.005$).

Compared to the control group, total swimming distance was similar in the s.c. and i.p. MK-801 groups (doses, 0.01 and 0.05 mg/kg) 24 h after the last training session (Table 3). Rats treated with the highest dose (0.1 mg/kg) of MK-801 via the s.c. or i.p. route displayed significantly decreased swimming distance on the probe day compared to rats in the control group ($F_{(6,48)} = 11.56, p < 0.0001$) (Table 3). Total swimming distance was shorter only following the administration of the highest MK-801 dose (0.1 mg/kg) via the s.c. route compared to the same dose given via the i.p. route.

Animals in the saline group swam significantly longer distances in the target quadrant compared to those in all MK-801 treatment groups in the probe trial carried out 24 h following the last training day ($F_{(6,48)} = 21.22, p < 0.0001$) (Table 3). Swimming distance in the target quadrant was shorter only following the administration of the highest MK-801 dose (0.1 mg/kg) via the s.c. route compared to the i.p. route

Table 3. Administration route-related and dose-dependent effects of MK-801 on retention parameters in the MWM task.

Treatment	Total swimming distance (cm)	Swimming distance in target quadrant (cm)	Number of crossings of target quadrant (number)	Latency to the first occurrence of target quadrant crossing (s)
Control: Saline	1345 ± 56.4	702 ± 43.6	4.5 ± 0.33	4.6 ± 0.70
MK-801, 0.01 mg/kg, s.c.	1486 ± 58.7	574 ± 37.4*	4.4 ± 0.57	6.2 ± 1.63
MK-801 0.01 mg/kg, i.p.	1403 ± 73.5	549 ± 44.9*	4.7 ± 0.52	4.9 ± 0.61
MK-801 0.05 mg/kg, s.c.	1407 ± 79.6	408 ± 39.2*	3.9 ± 0.34	9.4 ± 0.88*
MK-801 0.05 mg/kg, i.p.	1370 ± 74.4	468 ± 26.6*	5.3 ± 0.67	6.8 ± 1.44
MK-801 0.1 mg/kg, s.c.	814 ± 49.0* [#]	147 ± 17.9* [#]	1.4 ± 0.2* [#]	22.9 ± 4.03* [#]
MK-801 0.1 mg/kg, i.p.	1045 ± 82.1*	332 ± 46.6*	3.0 ± 0.62	7.2 ± 1.33

Each value represents mean (± SEM) for the MK-801 group (n=7) and the saline group (n=13). Significant differences were found using one-way ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls post-hoc test. *p < 0.05 vs. saline control group. #p < 0.05 vs. the corresponding i.p.-dosed animals.

The number of crossings in the target quadrant was significantly decreased in the group s.c.-administered 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 24 h after the last training session compared to the same dose of MK-801 delivered via the i.p. route ($F_{(6,48)} = 6.415, p < 0.0001$) (Table 3). The latency to the first crossing of the target quadrant was significantly increased following s.c. administration of 0.05 and 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 24 h after the last training day (Table 3). To add, subcutaneous administration of 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 led to a significantly longer latency to the first target quadrant crossing when compared to the same dose administered via the i.p. route ($p < 0.05$).

A summary of administration route-related and dose-dependent effects of MK-801 on behavioral responses in the MWM task is shown in Table 4. These results indicate that administering MK-801 via the s.c. route caused a greater impairment in

learning and memory in rats than i.p. treatment at the same dose. The most suitable dose of MK-801 to impair learning and memory without affecting motor function was identified as 0.05 mg/kg (Table 4). Delivering this dose via the i.p. route did not impair learning, but a dose of 0.1 mg/kg could impair learning alone, on the first two days of administration. Administering a higher dose (0.1 mg/kg) via both routes not only induced learning and memory impairments but also led to sensorimotor dysfunction.

Table 4. Administration route-related and dose-dependent effects of MK-801 on behavioral responses in the MWM task.

	MK-801 (mg/kg)					
	0.01		0.05		0.1	
	s.c.	i.p.	s.c.	i.p.	s.c.	i.p.
Learning impairment in 5 days	-	-	+++++	-	+++++	++
Memory impairment 24 h after last training	+	+	+	+	+	+
Motor dysfunction in training session in 5 days	-	-	-	-	++++	+

“-” – no effect

“+” – significant effect on experimental days (+ effect present for one day, ++ effect present for two days, etc.)

4. Discussion

We compared the effects of administering MK-801 using the two most commonly used routes (i.p. and s.c.) on its bioavailability in blood plasma and brain tissue, as well as on spatial learning and memory. For the first time, we have shown that there are higher MK-801 concentrations in brain tissue and blood plasma after s.c. administration than i.p. administration. In the present study, we directly compared the effects of MK-801 administered via the s.c. and i.p. routes under the same experimental setting. This activity revealed more pronounced learning disabilities and impaired memory function in the MWM task for animals treated via the s.c. route than i.p. route, even when the same dose of MK-801 was administered.

Our findings demonstrate that the concentration of MK-801 in brain and blood were higher in animals treated via the s.c. than i.p. route. The bioavailability of lipophilic drugs is known to be higher after s.c. than i.p. injection for compounds such as alkaloid ibogaine, morphine, and methamphetamine [39-41]. The concentration of phencyclidine, a non-competitive antagonist of the NMDA receptor, is approximately 4-fold higher in blood and brain tissue following s.c. administration than i.p. administration [41]. MK-801 is first transported to the liver when administered via the i.p., but not s.c. route. Cytochrome P450 is known to metabolize phencyclidine, an analog of MK-801, to several metabolites in the liver [42]. Moreover, the concentration of cytochrome P450 in the brain is merely 2% of that within the liver [43]. The underlying mechanism of drug absorption following s.c. administration is not understood very well [44], but it is known that lipophilic drugs can cross the blood-brain barrier by diffusion, without a special transporter. This is especially true for molecules with molecular weights lower than 600 Da, such as MK-801 and its salts [45,46]. This diffusion may explain the increased bioavailability of MK-801 in the brain after s.c. administration compared to i.p. administration. We also observed that in both species (i.e., rats and mice), the bioavailability of MK-801 is better after s.c. than i.p. administration. Taken together, our data suggest that the route of administration is a crucial determinant of MK-801 concentration in the blood and brain tissue, which determines the behavior of animals after MK-801 administration.

Behavioral responses in the MWM task are highly dependent on the route used to administer MK-801, and this corresponds to the bioavailability results in our experiment. Administering MK-801 at the most popular doses of 0.1 and 0.15 mg/kg impairs spatial learning and memory [6,24-27,30,47]. Therefore, when 0.1 mg/kg of MK-801 was delivered via the i.p. route to Wistar rats, we observed a significant impairment in memory and spatial learning, but this only occurred on the first two training days; this finding agrees with the results reported by Kesslak et al. [31]. This result suggests that this dose and administration route is insufficient to induce learning impairment in Wistar rats. The most commonly used dose for administering MK-801 via the s.c. route is 0.05 mg/kg [7,32,33], and in our study, this dose significantly impaired spatial learning in all training days and memory in the MWM task in Wistar rats. After 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 was administered via the s.c. route, learning was observed during the training days, but this was at a slower rate than in the control group. In contrast, the ability to learn platform position was not observed for rats administered 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the s.c. route. Consistent with the results of previous studies [14,27], we observed that administering 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. route did not affect learning, but significantly impaired memory. One may speculate that the better and faster bioavailability of MK-801 after s.c. administration more greatly and clearly compromised learning and memory in the MWM task relative to i.p. administration. Thus, only s.c. administration of 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 is suitable for investigating spatial learning and memory and is also appropriate for evaluating novel drugs with cognitive-enhancing properties.

Administering MK-801 did not only impair spatial learning and memory but caused the unwanted side effect of locomotor dysfunction. By administering 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the two routes (i.p. and s.c.), we saw a decrease in the swimming speed of rats during the training sessions, which suggests that MK-801 adversely affects sensorimotor abilities. In addition, we saw a more pronounced effect when MK-801 was administered via the s.c. route; a result due to its higher bioavailability as discussed previously. Subcutaneous administration of a 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 dose led to aberrant behavior, such as diving and the inability of rats to sit on the platform. These findings are consistent with those reported by Åhlander et al. [32] as they found that injecting MK-801 via the s.c. route leads to disturbances in sensorimotor processing and thus, reduces stay-on-platform time. Impaired sensorimotor function in

rats after i.p. injections of 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 has also been reported [6]. Therefore, learning and memory deficits in rats treated with 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 cannot be dissociated from impaired sensorimotor function. In most studies that mention impaired motor function, MK-801 was used at doses of 0.08 mg/kg and higher, implying that the results obtained herein should be carefully evaluated since learning and memory were disrupted by motor disturbances. Previously, swimming speed was demonstrated to be inversely proportional to MK-801 dose, which could be associated with sensorimotor dysfunction. Thus, this may have additional effects on memory [32]. We observed that MK-801 administered at all doses via the i.p. and s.c. routes resulted in rats achieving a shorter swimming distance in the target quadrant during the retention sessions (24 h after the last training), which could be associated with memory impairments. Administering 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. and s.c. routes reduced the total swimming distance, which could be attributed to sensorimotor disturbance. Sensorimotor dysfunction interfered with the animals' ability to learn the platform's location. This dysfunction may also affect the action of new drugs using this model and restrict the evaluation of their effects on cognition. Taken together, our data suggest that the most suitable and effective MK-801 dose to impair learning on all trial days, and memory during the probe trial, without affecting motor function, was 0.05 mg/kg administered via the s.c. route.

Several studies have emphasized that the effects of MK-801 on processes such as learning and memory could differ among rat strains. By referring to Table 1, such influence can be inferred. Sprague-Dawley, Wistar, and Long-Evans are the most commonly used rat strains for MWM task, and processes such as spatial learning and memory performance are feeble in Sprague-Dawley rats compared to Wistar rats in this task [48]. Nonetheless, Long-Evans rats have one of the best learning and memory functions among all rat strains [48], and when spatial learning in Wistar rats is compared to that in Long-Evans rats after administering 0.1 mg/kg MK-801 via the i.p. route, a significant impairment observed in Wistar rats [29]. Wistar rats were used in our experiments, and we observed that after administering 0.05 mg/kg MK-801 to these rats via the s.c. route, only learning and memory impairments could be observed (i.e., no sensorimotor disturbance). Interestingly, we could not find any previous studies where an MK-801 dose less than 0.05 mg/kg was administered to Wistar rats via the i.p. route. However, when this strain was injected with MK-801 doses up to

0.1 mg/kg, sensorimotor dysfunction and learning and memory impairments were observed in the MWM task [5,6]. Furthermore, spatial memory was significantly impaired after chronic i.p. administration of MK-801 in the MWM task in Long-Evans rats, but not in Wistar rats [49]. The gender of an animal can affect learning and memory processes. In fact, it has been shown that male Long-Evans rats could learn the platform position better than female rats [50,51], and male Wistar rats showed better spatial learning than female rats. However, there was no difference in spatial memory between male and female rats [52]. These results suggest that to achieve correct readouts, the genetic background (strain) and gender of an animal should be considered during the planning stage of an experiment. Other influencing factors such as the route of administration [7,29,32] and dose [7,32] should also be considered.

In conclusion, we observed a higher MK-801 concentration in brain tissue and blood plasma after s.c. than i.p. administration. Additionally, administering a dose of 0.05 mg/kg via the s.c. route resulted in impairments in spatial memory and learning (on all training days and without locomotor disturbances); however, this did not occur after i.p. administration. The present study allows for the selection of an appropriate administration route and dose based on the aim and design of the experiment.

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